

Analysis of Service Quality of Pakistani Restaurants

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Abstract

The main aim of my study is to add some part to the literature of service quality of Restaurant Industry. The research is undertaken from the perspective of restaurant industry in Pakistan and customer perception. In my research there are total five variables; Tangibility, Reliability, Responsiveness, Assurance & Empathy. These variables play a significant role in measuring service quality. In the last part, there is a complete data analysis, finding and suggestions for the restaurant industry to improve their service quality.

Keywords: Service Quality, Pakistani Restaurants, Industry.

Introduction:

Eating is a habitual activity for everyone. The choice of restaurants is influenced by a person's conscious or subconscious criteria. The importance attributed to these dining attributes is processed in the customer's mind, leading to a purchasing decision. Various factors, such as age, companionship, and social class, play a role in emphasizing these attributes, which then inform the customer's dining choices.

This has seen within the promotion of strong & well known brands like pizza hut, dominos etc. These restaurants attract customers only through their services, advertisement & loyalty and increase their retention rate. The importance of the perceived quality so as to induce the retention result in restaurant diligence is the main component to retain consumers and the business also. The major reason behind high growth of this industry is minimum entry barriers, anyone will simply enter into business because investment needed for those not covered the higher area .

Lahore is very famous because of the eating, enjoying and lively nature of its residents. The people of this region are fond of eating and trying new things. A true Lahorie is one whose primary love of life is FOOD. Passion of food in Lahore is increasing continuously.

Lahories mention it, create it and consume it in massive quantities. Lahorises love their meat and no meal is complete without a variety of dishes. New restaurants are opening frequently and its business is very economical. Several restaurants are open till the late night. For a past few years, people of our country do not have any particular entertainment and entertaining facilities. So ultimately most people focus on dining facilities in different restaurants.

Because of the rapid growth and fame of this business, we thought to check serviceability and perception of people regarding different fast food restaurants of Lahore.

Some are very renowned and proficient in their field but they are many in numbers and it's not possible for us to consider all of them so we decided to take 3,4 restaurants and we are going figure

out the best or most favorite among those restaurants regarding serviceability according to customer perceptions.

Pakistan is a developing country and having a huge population. There is a huge invasion of foreign businesses like fast food restaurants. Young and mature people are the target of these franchises. The focus of these restaurants is on service quality & customer satisfaction. They are basically two main concepts of service quality.

Fast food restaurants are very beneficial for developing countries because of their multinational brands. These brands improve the living standard of economy. As the trend changes, the younger generation is becoming habitual for outdoor dining and it leads to better quality of food, environment & services. At totally different occasions hosts additionally value more highly to bring guests to restaurants instead of serving them. Restaurants owing to the higher food style, pleasant atmosphere, reasonable value and sensible service that once more are contrary to native tradition of domestic welcome.

Literature Review:

Service quality is a critical factor in business, as it significantly impacts customer perceptions. The quality of customer service, in conjunction with the product, shapes these perceptions, as highlighted by Perrone and Ward.

Miller, Hardgrave, and Jones acknowledge the foundational research in service quality by Parasuraman, Zeithaml, and Berry in the mid-1980s. These pioneers were among the first to assert that quality concepts applicable in the goods sector are also relevant in the services sector.

Parasuraman, Zeithaml, and Berry delved into the assessment of service quality by analyzing consumer focus groups. As noted by Miller, Hardgrave, and Jones, their 1985 study revealed a frequent discrepancy between the expected and perceived levels of service experienced by consumers.

The significance of conceptualizing and measuring service quality is further underscored in the studies by Parasuraman, Zeithaml, Berry, Grönroos, and Eigiier and Langeard, as cited by Nyeck, Morales, Ladhari, and Pons.

One of the key contributions in this field, as pointed out by Jain and Gupta, was made by Parasuraman, Zeithaml, and Berry in 1988. They succinctly defined service quality as a "global judgment, or attitude, relating to the superiority of the service."

The Four different attributes of services make it tougher for service quality evaluation as comparisons to goods. It makes customer satisfaction very complicated but also gives competitive advantage. Service managers assigned the duties to understand and meet the challenges if they want to get success in this complex competitive environment

Technical quality is the quality of the service product (sometimes called the 'outcome dimension'). It is called Technical Customer Service Performance (TCSP). For example, in the case of a haircut the TCSQ will be the outcome in terms of the finished product.

Functional quality is defined as the manner in which the customer receives the service product (sometimes called the 'process-related dimension'), that is the manner in which the haircut was provided, which is commonly called 'customer service'. This aspect is called Functional Customer Service Performance (FCSP). (Perrone and Ward)

In line with the propositions put forward by Grönroos (1982) and Smith and Houston (1982), Parasuraman, Zeithaml and Berry (1985, 1988) posited and operationalized service quality as a difference between consumer expectations of 'what they want' and their perceptions of 'what they get.'

Based on this conceptualization and operationalization, they proposed a service quality measurement scale called 'SERVQUAL.' The SERVQUAL scale constitutes an important landmark in the service quality literature and has been extensively applied in different service settings. (Jain and Gupta)

In this decade, proficient and professional restaurant services are very important for every event like celebrations, dinings & in catering services etc. Restaurants' demand is very high and this work requires lots of patients. Company's success depends upon its reputation.

Entertainment is the most important factor for consumer satisfaction. Young & adults are the major targeted segment of these restaurants. If they are not providing entertainment then they can never give satisfaction to employees. Services are intangible physical environment & services have an enormous impact on customer satisfaction

Research Methodology

The purpose of this study is to observe and quantify customer satisfaction with the worth of services received from the specified restaurants. For this study analysis, I adopted questionnaire from the studies of different authors like Zeithaml, Stevens etc. The whole questionnaire depends on three parts, First part collect the demographic information (age, gender, income etc)

Approximately 200 questionnaires distributed in colleges, universities and restaurants operating in Lahore. Equal amount of questionnaires distributed in all specified places. The nature of the study is cross sectional and data collected from regular visits and in different time slots. I have selected the restaurants on the basis of its brand & image. Hopefully feedback will entirely on a voluntary basis.

The primary aim of this research is to conduct a Gap Analysis, focusing on comparing the Perception and Expectation scores of customers at Pizza Hut and Domino's Restaurant. This segment will delve into a detailed discussion of the objectives of the study.

Figure 1 illustrates the overall research design for Phase I. A questionnaire already was pre-designed. A review of the literature showed a previous scale measuring this construct. The questionnaire has total three sections. Section one gives the demographic information, section two contains and collects the feedback from respondents on independent variables and section three assembles the feedback from dependent variables. Data collection of my questionnaire was made only in the perspective of Lahore. Questionnaire was filled by 150 respondents in total. To find the reliable and generalize findings, I divided the questionnaires in equal number across my specified universities.

Figure 1: Research design flowchart

All statistical analyses will be performed using SPSS (version 15.0) and are discussed in the following section.

The questionnaire will request respondents to evaluate the restaurant on measurement scales or respective questions. There are total 12 questions approximately that are needed by any customer to answer.

In the year 2000, Dillman pioneered the Tailored Design Method (TDM) for conducting survey research. The main objective of this method, as described by Dillman, is to "foster trust in respondents and to enhance their perception of greater benefits and minimized costs in participating, while also aiming to substantially reduce survey errors" (Dillman, 2000, p.5). In alignment with Dillman's approach, data in this study will be meticulously gathered, tabulated, and recorded.

In my studies, data was collected from 150 respondents' through close ended questions. The response rate was 83%. Data was evaluated electronically by using Microsoft Excel and SPSS software. The major aim of this study, is to investigate and evaluate the relationship between service quality and customer satisfaction. Firstly, Data was coded in SPSS then investigate by applying box plots.

For measurement of reliability analysis a questionnaire has been developed to measure the reliability of my research. For measurement of reliability Cronbach's alpha is employed. The sample of my studies was approximately 125 questionnaires. If Cronbach's alpha is equal to 0.78 or greater than 0.78 then we can say that instrument is acceptable.

The reliability of research variables are given below;

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.780	10

According to researchers, the acceptable measurement of reliability is 78%. In my research, result of reliability testing of the tool used in this study is exactly 0.78 so it is satisfactory for the further analysis. It is very ordinary in psychological study to collect several measures of the identical construct. As mentioned above questionnaire was designed to measure the service quality of Pakistani restaurants and tangibility, reliability, responsiveness, assurance & empathy are its different variables which collectively measure the level of service quality.

Qualification

Respondents of my research are university going students. I selected the students of UCP, Punjab Group of Colleges and UET. As per my questionnaire there are only two categories where all students can fall; Graduate and Masters. In my studies, 35% respondents are Graduate and 87% are doing or have done their masters. 8%-10% did not mention their qualification.

Marital Status:

In universities only a few students are married. Mostly students have single marital status. As graphs shows only 40% students are married, 65% are single and 18% to 20% are those students who did not mention their marital status basically they are unknown people.

Age:

In questionnaire there are four categories of variable Age. Ranks are following

- 1) 18-24
- 2) 25-30
- 3) 31-40;
- 4) 41-50.

Mostly respondents are students so they fall in the category of young people. 55% of respondents falls in the 1st rank. 42% falls in 2nd rank (25-30). 6 to 7% people are belongs to 3rd age group (31-40). Rank 4 have approximately 13% respondents. 8% people do not mention their age.

Income:

Mostly university students do not enter in their field work. Higher rank of the above graph shows those respondents who do not earn their own. In Pakistan, mostly students depends on their parents earnings. Income graph shows the following ranks;

- 1) Unknown
- 2) 20000-30000
- 3) 31000-40000
- 4) 41000-50000
- 5) 51000 or above

Respondents who do not enter in the market or not have any source of income are 45 approximately. 29 people fall in the category who earn 20000-30000 monthly. Round about 31 respondents earn 31000-40000 monthly. Rank 4 (41000-50000) only have 12 respondent and 9 people falls in last rank which have 51000 or above salaried people.

Gender:

In my studies, I have also done the gender analysis and above graph shows that number of females are very high then males. Approximately, 72% respondents are females and 46% are males. Some of the respondents did not mention their gender. People who did not mention their gender are approximately 1%-2% only.

Conclusion:

In this project, the analysis of two prominent fast food restaurants in Pakistan, Pizza Hut and Domino's, was conducted using SPSS software. The study found that Pizza Hut holds a preference among customers, attributed to its facilities and reliability within the Pakistani restaurant industry. Customers show a tendency to favor dining in an environment that is not only hygienic and reliable but also holds a strong reputation.

Recommendations:

Pizza Hut:

To enhance the customer experience, the restaurant should focus on introducing innovative items to the menu, ensuring the dining area is comfortably arranged with tables spaced sufficiently to allow for private conversations. It's important to maintain a calm dining atmosphere, avoiding overcrowding that can lead to excessive noise levels. Additionally, prioritizing quick service should be a key aspect of the restaurant's operational focus.

Domino's:

To enhance customer perception and satisfaction, the restaurant must engage in proactive advertising and clearly identify and target their market segment. It's crucial for employees, including telephone operators and call center staff, to receive rigorous training for efficient

customer interaction and quick response times, from order placement to delivery. Additionally, the restaurant should focus on offering a friendly and helpful workforce to address customer queries, innovate their menu offerings, and ensure staff, particularly waiters and managers, are well-dressed, energetic, and motivated. Regular assessments and training for employees are necessary to maintain and improve service quality. The restaurant should also offer discounts and special deals, increase advertising to reinforce customer recall and demonstrate care, empathize with customers during any issues, and reward regular customers with special discounts, possibly by maintaining a customer record system.

Limitation

The study, while comprehensive, does face certain limitations. These include a potential bias in the sample selection, as the data is drawn from a specific demographic and geographic location, which may not represent the broader population. Additionally, the reliance on self-reported data can introduce subjectivity, potentially affecting the accuracy of the findings. The study's timeframe and resource constraints also limit the scope of analysis and depth of research, which might affect the generalizability of the results. Furthermore, the rapidly changing dynamics of the industry mean that the findings might not fully capture the latest market trends or shifts in consumer behavior.

References

1. Ali, F , Khan, A., S , Rehman, F (2012, July) AN ASSESSMENT OF THE SERVICE QUALITY USING GAP ANALYSIS: A STUDY CONDUCTED AT CHITRAL, PAKISTAN *INTERDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF CONTEMPORARY RESEARCH IN BUSINESS* retrieved (2013, 10th october) from <http://journal-archives20.webs.com/259-266.pdf>
2. Valarie A. Zeithaml and Mary Jo. Bitner (1996) "Services Marketing" Parasuraman, Valarie A. Zeithaml and Leonard Berry (1988) "SERVQUAL: A Multiple Item Scale for Measuring Customer Perceptions of Service Quality"
3. Robert E. Miller, Bill Hardgrave and Thomas W. Jones "The Impact of Presentation Order on Service Quality Dimensions"
4. Anthony Perrone and Antony Ward "Enhancing the Gronroos Model of Service Quality"
5. Sanjay K. Jain and Garima Gupta "Measuring Service Quality: SERVQUAL VS SERVPERF Scale"
6. Fareena Sultan and Merlin C .Simpson "International Service Variants: Restaurant Customer Expectations and Perceptions of Service Quality"
7. Simon Nyeck, Miguel Morales, Riadh Ladhari and Frank Pons "10 Years of Service Quality Measurement: Reviewing the Use of the SERVQUAL Instrument"
8. Malik, S., A , Jaswal, L., H , Malik, S., A , Awan , T., M (2013, 21st February) *Measuring Service Quality Perceptions of the customers of restaurants in Pakistan*. Retrieved (2014, 10th October) from <http://www.cqm.rs/ijqr/journal/v7-n2/2.pdf>
9. Anwar, S. , Gulzar, A (n.d) IMPACT OF PERCEIVED VALUE ON WORD OF MOUTH ENDORSEMENT AND CUSTOMER SATISFACTION: MEDIATING ROLE OF REPURCHASE INTENTIONS *International Journal of Economics and Management Sciences* retrieved (2014, 10th Oct) from <http://www.omicsonline.com/open-access/2162-6359/2162-6359-1-042.pdf?aid=17160>